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Keeping Up With Technological Progress: Towards An Understanding Of AI Access, Acceptance, And Use among Administrative Staff In Selected Universities In Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The emergence and proliferation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) have triggered significant transformations in administrative processes globally and there is every need to understand how administrative staff in universities engage with this technology in their daily tasks. This study examines the perception, accessibility, and practical use of AI tools among non-teaching staff of selected universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, to understand how they keep up with technological progress. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and a mixed methods research design were used and this involves a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches to data collection and analysis. It made use of a convenience sample of 160 senior non-teaching staff and 12 top management staff consisting of registrars, ICT directors, deputy vice-chancellors of administration, and unit heads, selected through convenience and purposive sampling techniques respectively. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire and an interview guide while relying on the use of descriptive and thematic approaches for data analysis. Drawing from the analysis, the findings show that administrative staff in the selected universities have better awareness of AI, but access to and use of AI platforms for administrative tasks are relatively low. It also shows that AI acceptance and use are largely influenced by factors such as institutional support, digital literacy, and a lagged behaviour. The study concludes that AI acceptance, access, and use remain largely uneven and shaped by several factors. It recommends that the management team of the universities should make a conscious attempt to scale up digital literacy and inclusive AI deployment.

Keywords: Technological progress, AI Access, Acceptance, Use, Administrative Staff, Universities, Bayelsa State.

INTRODUCTION

Although there is a growing concern about the increasing integration and proliferation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into all spheres of human endeavours, history has shown that reversing technological progress has always been difficult. This presents one possible lookahead, which is that AI is most likely here to stay despite the widespread concern about its ability to undermine humanity in many ways.

Additionally, there is no doubting the fact that AI has provided the enabling platform that is necessary to transform not just how individuals perform their daily tasks but how institutions produce and reproduce their material deliverables. Generative AI platforms such as ChatGPT, Gemini, perplexity, and many others continue to change the way work is done with huge transformations in administrative processes across different sectors around the world (Russell & Norvig, 2021) and higher education institutions, such as the universities are not left out.

Although AI has permeated all sectors with an earthquake effect that comes with massive reengineering of the way work is organized and delivered, nowhere has this been more impactful than the knowledge industry and importantly, the university system. Thus, universities as one of the hubs of knowledge and innovation, are more susceptible the impact of AI and its integration, especially when one considers the fact that this technology has transformed several key activities such as automating grading systems, personalizing learning platforms, and providing advanced tools for data analytics. Despite the growing issues surrounding productive integrity within the university system, particularly among students and lecturers, AI remains a transformative tool for institutional management and it is fast becoming a model direction for progressive universities worldwide (Popenici & Kerr, 2017). This trend presents a clarion call for researchers at all fronts to engage in studies that will guide the understanding of the revolutionary role and impact of AI with regard to how workers engage with and adapt to the different AI platforms within the business ecosystem.

Like every new technological progress in the world, the emergence of AI has triggered a huge body of empirical studies that are aimed at understanding the impact on human activities and as would be expected, most of the research endeavours have been focused on how these tools affect the university system. What is particularly glaring in these researches, is the troubling outcomes that support age-long digital divide between and within regions of the world. For instance, in the developed regions, AI mainstreaming into university activities, particularly as a function of deliberate policy interventions has been largely commendable. This is perhaps driven by the robustness of existing digital infrastructures, commensurable investment in technological innovation, and a proactive regulatory mindset. Discussing this in the context of evolution and revolution, Roll and Wylie (2016) argued that the trajectory of AI mainstreaming into university activities has been mostly successful in regions such as North America and Western Europe, given the openness of these regions to integrate AI usage in academic activities beyond just the classroom to administrative tasks. Popenici and Kerr (2017) including Breazeal et al. (2024) contextualized this argument more precisely when they noted that institutions like the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and the University of Oxford have integrated AI-powered systems to deal with tasks that range from admissions processing, course scheduling, financial management, to research administration, and this is supported by strong regulations with significant priority for data privacy, equitable access, and of course, ethical usage. This is in addition to ensuring digital literacy for all staff and students with conscious efforts to limit cases of digital divides (European Commission, 2021).

However, while there is a measure of progress in terms of AI policy frameworks and strategies at the aggregate levels from a continental perspective and at country levels, the ability to trickle down these strategic frameworks and plans of action sectorially and at the institutional level remain a challenge. For instance, the readiness of the African Union to align with the global trend in AI technology is evident in its Continental Artificial Intelligence Strategy, where it notes its support for an Africa-centric approach to harnessing the benefits of AI (see Africa Union, 2024). Perhaps in a bid to align with the aspirations of the African Union, several countries within the region have developed a country-specific AI strategy or policy framework and this includes South Africa's National Artificial Intelligence Policy Framework, Kenya's Artificial Intelligence, Ghana's National Artificial Intelligence Strategy, and of course Nigeria's National Artificial Intelligence Strategy, among others. Although these attempts at providing national strategic directions for AI deployment and use across several countries in Africa are welcome developments, several institutions continue to operate without or outside any coordinated approach or structure that ensures that national strategies are felt. Clearly, the aspiration to harness AI exists across Africa but structural-historical challenges continue to downplay this willingness. For instance, in Nigeria,

the transformative potential of AI often collides with familiar challenges such as shortage of financial resources, inadequate digital technology, digital literacy even among working populations, and unreliable power supply (Ughulu, 2025). These factors continue to provide both institutional and individual reasons that limit the effective access, acceptance and usage of AI tools, with outcomes that lead to disparities in AI integration progress compared to developed regions of the world (Akinwalere & Ivanov, 2022). This often create conditions for lagger behaviours to occur among workers or staff of academic institutions in countries like Nigeria, where the adoption and integration of emerging technologies is slow, despite the recognition of associated benefits.

Given the knowledge associated with the previous literature on AI access and use in Africa and, especially in Nigeria, it is important for a study of this nature that is aimed at providing institutional understanding of how AI is conceived of, accessed and used for administrative purposes in the universities. This study investigates how non-teaching staff in three universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, keep up with technological progress, with the aim of understanding how AI access, acceptance, and use. Essentially, the study addresses three key questions: What is the extent of institutional support in areas such as infrastructure provision and training interventions and how does this influence the level of AI access and use among administrative staff in selected universities in Bayelsa State?; Does digital literacy level among non-teaching staff influence the acceptance and use of AI tools for administrative tasks in these universities?; and To what extent does the lagger behaviour among non-teaching staff impact on the level of adoption and use of AI tools in administrative tasks in the universities?

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: Conceptual model for AI Access & Practical Use

Fig. 1 above shows the conceptual framework for this study and it clearly shows the link between key concepts. It is easy to see that at the primary driver of AI access, adoption, and practical use is institutional support, which encompasses effective leadership and digital infrastructure provision. Agarwal and Prasad (1997) note that making progress in terms of digital technology uptake at the institutional level requires top management support for tech adoption and capacity building among staff. This conscious attempt by leadership provides the necessary conditions to scale up digital consciousness, and by extension, literacy. Mutula and Wamukoya (2007) draw attention to the foundational importance of institutional support in migrating from one level of technological knowledge to another, while consciously addressing digital divides within an organization. The figure also takes cognizance of the presence of lagger who tend to cling to old ways of doing tasks or even resist change, notwithstanding

the institutional enablement to suck in technologies into the culture of work. This ordinarily fits into the theoretical frame of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), where factors like perceived usefulness, willingness to adopt, and perceived ease of use combine to determine what category of people stay within and outside the lagger domain. This analogy sits well with previous studies on technology adoption as most scholars agree despite having high digital literacy skills, hesitancy and resistance to change may trigger a behaviour that delays adoption of new technologies like AI (Teo, Lee, & Chai, 2007). However, even with laggards in the technology acceptance framework, it is believed that the right institutional motivation can help moderate their behaviour and get them to adopt and use emerging technologies. Lastly, the diagram terminates by conveying the understanding that when staff perceive the usefulness of technologies such as AI, have the willingness to adopt, and find it easy to use, this can significantly enable practical application in administrative tasks. However, the successful application of technological platforms like AI depends largely on the availability of such tools further reinforcing the role of institutional support in promoting access, adoption, and use.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The old scare of digital divide remains a huge concern within the literature on the integration of AI in administrative activities globally. Thus, while amongst developed nations, AI has witnessed significant uptake by institutions, particularly in Higher Education Institutions in most developed countries, this is still a problem in developing nations where strategic AI policies have not sufficiently trickled down in terms of implementation. The ability to mainstream AI access and use into institutional administration in academics is dependent on several factors such as a digital transformative leadership, infrastructure, and policy frameworks that take cognizance of ethical use, data privacy, equitable access (European Commission, 2021). While evidence suggest that most African countries like Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, and South Africa, among others, have all curated their own country-specific AI policies, other factors continue to militate against the successful implementation of these strategic frameworks.

In Nigeria, like elsewhere in Africa, while AI awareness of the potentials of AI is high, the actual acceptance, access, and practical usage in university administration remain relatively low (Igbo et al., 2024). The potentials of AI to help in streamlining administrative tasks and improve student activities in Nigerian universities have been widely acknowledged by some literature, however, most of these literatures seem to have been mostly exploratory, with a significant reliance on mental calculations and systematic reviews as a basis for describing the benefits of AI in academic administration (see for instance; Eze et al., 2021; Ibrahim & Sulaiman, 2019). The potentials of AI to help scale up staff efficiency for optimum academic administration, notwithstanding, scholars have also highlighted some major impediments, which include inadequate digital infrastructure, particularly erratic power supply, limited internet connectivity, and low uptake of digital knowledge among staff (Abiolu & Akinyemi, 2025). Focusing on AI in library administration in Nigeria, Igbo et al. (2024) note that AI adoption in academic libraries is particularly very low due to the absence of policy frameworks, lack of digital infrastructure, and unskilled and semi-skilled manpower. The article by Igbo et al., corroborates previous studies such as those by Moustapha and Yusuf (2023) and Oyekele (2023), who both shared their dissatisfaction with the low level of AI adoption and use in Nigeria, when compared to other countries in the developed nations.

Although leadership willingness to provide basic digital infrastructure and also ensure that staff skills are updated to meet keep pace with advancements in technology are critical to the adoption, access and use of AI in academic administration, the level of existing digital knowledge amongst staff is has been considered by most scholars is also considered to be very crucial to AI integration. Ajonbadi, OLawoyin, and Adekoya (2023) note that the history of the divide in digital knowledge among a cohort of staff in any institution plays a key role in how emerging technologies are perceived, adopted, accessed, and applied in the work process. Additionally, these scholars exposed the fact that while there is a growing interest in the use of digital facilities in academic delivery, there is need for continuous training in order to enhance the skills of users to keep pace with new realities in the digital ecosystem.

The gaps in digital literacy brings us to the issue of lagger behaviour which is a subtle attitude that is geared towards resistance to adopting new technologies by some persons. While existing literature seem to share a consensus that leadership plays a sensitive role in ensuring that digital infrastructure and skills development match digital technology uptake in institutions, there is every need to understand that staff or workers' attitude to new technologies is also as important as leadership will. In this regard, the understanding of lagger behaviours becomes very crucial, especially as one study shared the view that most staff find it very difficult to accept new technologies and adapt them to their work (see Idhalama et al., 2023). This puts our understanding of lagger behaviour beyond the attitude of non-acceptance of new ways of working or new technologies, to a notion of lack of motion or even preference for traditional ways of working. In this sense, we also move beyond seeing this a general lack of skill to one that is deeply rooted in the psychology of staff who express fear of job displacement, unreliability of technology, or simply the comfort to stay with the status quo (Rogers, 2003). The lagger behaviour in our context takes us to the discussion on technology acceptance model, which is the subject of the next section.

Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

This study draws on the assumptions of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as proposed by Davies (1989). The TAM is considered to be one of the widely used models in terms of not just evaluating but also predicting user preferences and acceptance of technologies. Its basic assumptions, which we consider here as a motion of beliefs rests on the notion that the attitude of people towards technologies is predicated on two key but interlinked beliefs, these are perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) (Davies, 1989). While the former belief rests on the understanding that the level with which a person believes that a particular technology would enhance job performance defines behaviour towards such a technology, the latter conveys a notion that people would prefer to use technologies that are free of too much efforts (Al-Gahtani, 2004; Venkatesh, Speier, & Morris, 2002).

Although the use of the TAM in previous studies makes it seemingly a fatigued theoretical perspective for a research of this nature, our study extends the theory's core tenets given that it integrates contextual factors that are peculiar to universities in a developing nation like Nigeria. These relative indicators or variables are presented here as antecedents with significant influence on the core constructs of the TAM such as PU and PEOU, and by extension, AI acceptance and use. In other words, our study integrates variables such as institutional support, digital literacy, lagger behaviour into Davies's (TAM) core constructs (PU and PEOU) as a functional analytical framework that ultimately drives home the understanding of AI acceptance and use in administrative tasks within the universities selected for this study. In doing this, it is the intention of this study to prove that administrative staff working in these universities face not just variables that are internal to them as reflected in the TAM, but also external variables that moderate institutional readiness, individual behaviours, and technology uptake. Hence, beyond being a fit-for-purpose theory here, the TAM's strength is felt more in being amenable to the unique variables and contexts of our study.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Bayelsa state, one of the prominent petroleum host states in the South-South region of Nigeria. The research design adopted for the study is the mixed-methods strategy, particularly the convergent parallel approach that allows for a combination of both quantitative and qualitative techniques for data collection and analysis. While quantitative data helped to establish the breadth and prevalence of respondents' perception of the subject-matter of the study, qualitative data helped with the depth of reasons driving such perceptions and behaviours (see, Craswell & Plano, 2011). Although the study initially set out to adopt the simple random and purposive approaches, the fieldwork realities informed a change to convenience and purposive techniques, due to ease of access, cost-effectiveness, availability, and knowledge of the subject (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). Three universities in Bayelsa State, namely Federal University Otuoke, Niger Delta University, Amassoma, and University of

Africa, Toru-Orua, were purposively selected for this study because of their size. The quantitative aspect of the study involved the administration of a virtual Google form (questionnaire) to target 160 non-teaching/administrative staff and in-person, as well as telephone interviews with 12 senior administrative/teaching staff selected based on their administrative and technical roles in the universities. The interviewees include registrars, research and quality assurance directors, unit heads, and ICT directors in the selected universities. However, the study eventually recorded 148 questionnaire responses and only 4 interviews conducted across the three universities. This informed the data analysis and findings presented below. The method of data analysis involved the use of a triangulation technique that housed a mixed methods approach where descriptive tools such as percentages and frequencies were used for the quantitative data and excerpts or verbatim quotes from the qualitative data were applied to cross-validate the quantitative data.

RESULTS

The analysis is done here based on the three research questions that guide the data collection.

RQ 1: What is the extent of institutional support in areas such as infrastructure provision and training interventions and how does this influence the level of AI access and use among administrative staff in selected universities in Bayelsa State?

Figures 2 and 3 above collectively provide data that responds to research question one, which basically seeks to show the extent of institutional support in terms of infrastructure and training for staff and how these influences the level of AI access and practical use among non-teaching/ administrative staff across the three universities. Starting with Figure 2, the data on the extent to which institutional support is provided to administrative staff, particularly in terms of digital infrastructure and capacity building shows that out of the 82 Federal University Otuoke (FUO) respondents, 5% rated it very high, 56% rated it high, 29% said it was low, while 10% considered it to be very low. On the other hand, out the 51 participants from the Niger Delta University (NDU), a staggering 84% said institutional support was low, 8% reported that it was very low, while another 8% saw it as high. On the part of the 25 respondents that participated from University of Africa (UoA), 32% of the participants considered institutional support to be high, 52% said it was low, while 16% rated it as very low.

Figure 3 provided complementary data to the results presented above by showing how the level of institutional support influences staff access and use of AI tools in the selected universities. As a reflection of the institutional support, 61% of the respondents from FUO agreed that these supports, positively influenced their access and use of AI tools in administrative work, 29% of them disagreed, while 10% strongly disagreed. With regard to NDU, 61% of them disagreed, while 39% of them agreed. On the part of UoA, 24% of the participants agreed, 64% of them disagreed, while 12% of them strongly disagreed on whether institutional support has influenced their access and use of AI platforms.

Responses from the interviews provided deeper insights on why the questionnaire participants held the above views on institutional support and its influence on how administrative staff access and use AI in the various schools. For instance, the participants from FUO noted that the management of the university is very open to digitizing the entire

operations of the university, especially documentation and records keeping among other students related administrative tasks. This is particularly evident in the views of one of the participants who noted that:

In our University, the Vice-Chancellor is open to providing all the support that is needed including internet facilities across the different campuses to ensure that staff have the required access to use any kind of digital platform they deem fit that can improve on their works, including AI. (Interviewee 1/Male/FUO/20th June, 2025)

On the area of training, one other participant noted that:

Our management team in FUO had organized a comprehensive training on AI, even though the training did not teach the participants how to use the platforms, it however, created a massive awareness of AI in administrative and academic tasks making staff to become conscious. In fact, most staff now know about ChatGPT, Copilot, and Gemini AI among others, with most of them using ChatGPT more often now. However, one area that is lacking is the issue of not having an AI policy to guide ethical usage. (Interviewee 2/Female/FUO/20th June, 2025)

The above interviews provide significant support to the quantitative data presented in Figures 2 and 3 above because a significant number of the respondents from FUO believe that they have the institutional support to integrate AI into their work. Although, interview participants see these supports as modest, particularly as there is currently low internet coverage on the campuses and even where we have internet, service is very erratic. This notwithstanding, participants see this as moving in the right direction to digitize administrative activities in the university. Although FUO shows, moderate progress towards access and use of AI in administrative tasks, the other two universities suffer some setbacks in terms of institutional support. For NDU, there has not been any institutional infrastructure and or training directly targeting the use of AI in the university. However, one of the participants noted that:

“the management of NDU is just waking up to the reality of AI penetration in our university. As I speak with you, I have just been made to head a committee to draft an AI policy for the University and we are working on that. As for any formal training targeted at getting the staff to be institutionally aware of AI, that has not happened. (Interviewee 2/Male/NDU/14th June, 2025)

The above position clearly shows why the questionnaire respondents reported low levels of support from the NDU management on AI integration and this may have been the reason why they also reported low influence on how they access and use AI in administrative tasks. Although at the time of this analysis, the researchers were unable to reach any of the interviewees from UoA, there is every likelihood that the questionnaire response could point to the same direction as that of NDU regarding institutional support, access and use if AI amongst the staff.

RQ 2: Does digital literacy level among non-teaching staff influence the acceptance and use of AI tools for administrative tasks in these universities?

Figures 4 and 5 above provides data that address research question 2, which focuses on determining if digital literacy levels of respondents influence the acceptance and use of AI tools for their tasks as administrative staff in the universities selected. Overall, the responses are similar as Figure 4 shows that 27% of the participants from FUO strongly agreed, 57% of them agreed, while 16% of them disagreed. This shows that 84% of the participants believe that their digital skill is sufficient to accommodate AI

learning and usage. From NDU, 35% of the participants strongly agree, 33% of them agree, and 31% of them disagree. Although this is promising as 68% of participants in this university are sure that their digital skill is sufficient for AI learning and use, there is still a concern that 31% of administrative staff lack confidence in their ability to handle AI tools. Data from UoA presents similar outcome with that of FUU as 43% of the respondents strongly agreed, 44% of them agreed, and 10% of them disagree. This shows that a significant number of respondents trust their digital skills for AI learning and practical use. Figure 5 pushed the digital skills measure further by examining whether respondents view their digital literacy levels as having influence on their acceptance, access, and use of AI in their day-to-day administrative tasks. Data associated with FUU shows that 23% of the participants strongly agreed, 57% of them agreed, while 20% of them disagreed. This presents a similar pattern with the data in Figure 4 suggesting that beyond the confidence in their digital literacy skills, they recognize the fact that this skill has influenced their level of acceptance, access, and use of AI for their jobs. With regard to NDU, 10% of the respondents strongly agree that their digital literacy skill has positively influenced their acceptance, access, and use of AI, 74% of them agreed, 14% of them disagreed. Despite 31% of them having low confidence in terms of their digital skills as reported in Figure 4, a significant number of the NDU participants still believe that their digital skills have influenced their acceptance, access, and use of AI. On the part of UoA, 32% of the respondents strongly agreed, 60% agreed, and 8% of the participants disagreed. This data further reinforces the data in Figure 4 proving that participants from UoA are not just digitally enabled but also believe in the relevance of digital literacy skills in terms of AI adoption and application.

Additionally, data from the interviews with subject matter experts in the context of digital technology from the various universities shows that the interviewees' views align with that of the questionnaire respondents albeit with more deeper insights. For instance, one of the FUU interviewees noted that:

I think the digital training that was conducted recently for non-teaching staff in our university has also raised their digital literacy level and preparedness for AI uptake and use in administrative work. We should know or agree that the more someone has high digital skills, the more that person is likely to accept and use new technologies such as AI. (*Interviewee 2/Female/FUU/20th June, 2025*)

Although no institutionally-driven digital literacy training has been held for administrative staff at NDU, the interview participants also aligned their views with that of the interviewees from FUU. In this regard, one participant expressed the opinion that:

I think today most people have come to accept the fact that digital technology skill is a strong requirement if one has to survive the workplace and our staff have a good sense of that knowledge and I believe that if the management of the University see this as an advantage, they can train the staff on how to use the different but relevant AI tools for administrative works. (*Interviewee 4/Male/NDU/14th June, 2025*)

The results from both the quantitative and qualitative information analyzed above shows that participants from across the three universities sampled share a common perspective that digital literacy skill is critical to their acceptance, access, and use of AI platforms for their administrative tasks. However, there are behavioural dimensions to the understanding of how new technologies are received or even applied by individuals. This understanding led to the discussion on how the latter behaviour may impact on respondents' acceptance, access, and use of AI. This aspect of the study is addressed below.

RQ 3: To what extent does the lagger behaviour among non-teaching staff impact on the level of adoption and use of AI tools in administrative tasks in the universities?

Figure 6 and 7 address the third research question in this study, which examines the extent that lagger behaviour, particularly hesitancy and resistance to change can affect perceive ease of use in terms of AI as highlighted in the conceptual farmwork (see Fig. 1 above). Hence, the data presented in Figure 6 above captures respondents' opinion on whether they prefer to wait and see how new technologies perform before using them. The FOU data shows that 77% of the respondents agree that they often wait before using new technologies like AI, 23% of them disagreed. This clearly shows a significant level of hesitant (lagger) behaviour amongst the participants and an expression of the difference between infrastructural and psycho-behavioural barriers to AI acceptance, access, and usage. This is identical to the data from NDU participants, where 78% of them agreed and 22% of them disagreed. However, the data from UoA reveal a slightly resistance stance, with 44% of the respondents agreeing that they often wait to see how new technologies perform and that includes AI, and 56% of them disagreed.

Figure 7 extended our knowledge on how lagger behaviour can influence AI acceptance, access, and use further, especially with regard to the ease of transitioning from traditional methods to AI tools. Based on data gathered from FOU participants, 37% agreed that they are slow in transitioning to the use of AI for their official jobs, 46% disagree, while 17% strongly disagree. On the part of NDU, 39% of the participants agreed and 61% disagreed. For UoA, 16% of the respondents strongly agree that the transition is slow and challenging, 20% of them agreed, while 36% of them disagreed and 26% strongly disagreed. This result supports earlier data presented in Figure 4, where staff of UoA expressed significant confidence and willingness to adapt AI to their work.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data on institutional support, particularly the provision of digital infrastructure and training for administrative staff is considered a formative driver of acceptance, access, and use of digital technology including AI as captured in the conceptual framework (see Fig. 1). The finding in this regard reveals some form of disparity across the sampled universities. While FOU expressed a moderate level of institutional support due to leadership openness to digitization and awareness trainings on AI, NDU and UoA demonstrated low levels of perceptions concerning institutional support. This difference provides strong validation for the theoretical framework that holds institutional support as very critical external variable in terms of scaling up perceived usefulness (PU) of emerging technologies (in this case AI) in organizations. As explained by Abiolu and Akinyemi (2025), when institutions provide a clear strategic direction and support, a significant part of the barrier to technology acceptance, access, and use will be reduced. In our

research, the transformative role of leadership or management in FUO through AI awareness trainings is believed to have a major effect on how administrative staff perceive of and engage with AI in the university. This aligns with the findings of Agarwal and Prasad (1997) that transformative leadership is important in scaling up knowledge and use of new technologies. Furthermore, this finding supports that of Abiolu and Akinyemi (2025), which shows that deliberate AI trainings helped scale up acceptance and use among librarians in selected universities in the Western part of Nigeria. Although an AI policy drafting committee has been set up in NDU, the near absence of a FUO-like institutional support, as is also the case with UoA, limits the level of AI awareness and use in these institutions. This again supports the finding of Igbo et al. (2024) who noted that the inability of public organizations like the universities to provide institutional internet services and ICT trainings combine to undermine the digitization process in most of the institutions.

With regard to digital literacy level and its effect on acceptance, access, and usage of AI tools, findings across the sampled universities show that digital knowledge is very vital in shaping how participants accept, access, and use of AI. In other words, the study found that across all the universities, participants agree with the fact that their level of digital literacy plays a key role in how they perceive of, accept, access, and use AI in their administrative tasks. This shows that the higher the digital literacy level, the higher the chances of accepting, accessing, and using AI platforms by the respondents. This finding aligns significantly with the TAM assumption that a higher digital proficiency leads to commensurate level of perceived ease of use (PEOU) as indicated in the conceptual and theoretical framework sections of this study. This is because those who have higher digital literacy levels are more likely to appreciate the benefits of AI when compared with those that do not. Again, this is supported by one study conducted by Viskovic, Djeric, and Luic (2024) who found that among marketing professionals who self-assessed their digital literacy as high, the use of AI tools is quite easy and more frequent. This finding is particularly crucial to the understanding of the fact that while institutional support is very crucial, where this is unavailable, digital literacy levels at individual levels may help scale up ease of use among staff. This notwithstanding, we could also have a situation where the digital literacy level is high, but AI use and adoption still remain largely low (Emiri, Ijiekhuamhen, & Nwankwo, 2024), due to hesitancy and resistance, which we refer to in this study as a lagger behaviour.

Consequently, on how the lagger behaviour amongst administrative staff affects their adoption and use of AI tools in their jobs, this study found that, while institutional support and digital literacy are important, psycho-behavioural factors may reduce the level of AI acceptance, access, and use. Therefore, the finding reveals a high prevalence of lagger behaviour amongst participants and this shows that a substantial percentage of the respondents still lag behind in terms of AI access and usage as most of them prefer to wait and see how the technology performs before they use it for their administrative tasks. This psycho-behavioural factor suggests a weak diffusion of innovation or in the context of the TAM, low levels of acceptance due to perceived lack of personal will to switch easily to new technologies such as AI. For instance, drawing from data, even amongst FUO and UoA participants, who reported a moderate institutional support and high digital literacy, we still find a high percentage of lagger behaviour showing a psycho-behavioural (wait-and-see tendency) barrier to AI adoption and use. This supports the finding of Li, Ashraf, and Amin (2023), who submitted that resistance to change has a positive relationship with AI readiness, acceptance, access, and use among hospitality staff in Pakistan. Furthermore, the findings corroborate that of Idhalama et al (2023), who noted that despite high awareness levels amongst teaching staff in Nigerian universities, adoption and use of emerging technologies such as AI are still limited due partly to lack of facilities on the one hand, and a technology shy attitude among some staff on the other hand.

CONCLUSION

This study has examined how administrative staff keep up with technological progress in order to guide our understanding of how they access, accept, and use AI in their day-to-day tasks in selected universities in Bayelsa State. Based on the findings across the three universities sampled, it is clear that

while there is a commendable level of awareness and widespread confidence in their digital literacy levels, administrative staff's actual acceptance, access, and use of AI tools for the purpose of their jobs remain low. This is significantly shaped by the differentials in institutional support in terms of provision of digital infrastructure and AI trainings, individual digital competencies, and a prevalence of psycho-behavioural (lagger behaviour) disposition. The disparities in digital infrastructure provision and related capacity building for staff across the different universities stand out as the primary determinant of AI acceptance, access, and use, which strongly affirms the conceptual and theoretical frameworks in this study, particularly the TAM's emphasis on variables such as perceived ease of use as a function of institutional influence. Lastly, the prevalence of a lagger behaviour which is characterized by a wait-and-see (hesitancy) and to some extent a resistant to change attitude presents a psycho-behavioural understanding of delay in AI adoption among administrative staff across the selected universities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing from the findings and conclusion of this study, the following are recommendations that can scale up how administrative staff keep up with AI in the universities.

- i. There is need to prioritise digital infrastructure provision. The universities in Bayelsa State and indeed others in Nigeria, need to begin to prioritise investment in internet connectivity, and other digital technologies including AI across all campuses in the respective universities.
- ii. Conduct targeted AI trainings for staff. Notwithstanding the individual-based digital literacy among staff, the authorities in various universities need to develop and implement targeted hands-on training designed to improve AI knowledge for non-teaching and even teaching staff.
- iii. The need for a robust AI policy: From the interviews, it was discovered that only NDU has instituted a committee to produce an AI policy for the university. There is a need for the other universities to develop a clear AI policy drawing from Nigeria's National Artificial Intelligence Strategy.
- iv. Promote a progressive culture of innovation. The universities' management team should endeavour to encourage and reward staff who adopt new technologies, by providing a supportive environment to help in reducing lagger behaviour and promote easy uptake of new technologies.

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